

SINGLE PRECISION FLOATING POINT ARITHMETIC UNIT ARCHITECTURE AND ANALYSIS USING VERILOG

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ABSTRACT: The multimode, single-precision floating-point arithmetic unit written in Verilog Hardware Description Language is detailed in this article. The multimode floating point arithmetic unit may be propagated, divided, added to, or subtracted from. The intended result is to physically evaluate the suggested notion using the Zed Board Zynq Evaluation and Creation Kit (xc7z020clg484-1). An efficient multimode floating point arithmetic unit for the IEEE 754 floating point number system is our aim, with the hope that it will lead to better hardware deployment. By combining the addition and subtraction units with the multiplication and division units, as well as the four individual units for the four arithmetic operations, we may optimise these combined units to minimise the amount of LUTs in the FPGA. This reduces the overall space needed by the gear.

KEYWORDS: *Floating Point, Look Up Tables (LUTs), VERILOG, HDL, Adder, Multiplier.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In essence, floating point values are just real binary numbers. Floating point arithmetic operations are widely employed in commercial, financial, and web-based applications. The multimode computation is fundamental to the scientific applications. To eliminate unnecessary multiplication and avoid underflow, multimode-based computation is used. In recent times, FPGA has made accessible a vast variety of registers, microprocessors, hardware multipliers, and LUTs (LUTs) [1]. Many efforts have been undertaken in the last few decades to make

floating-point calculations more efficient. In addition to being more energy-and space-intensive than fixed-point multipliers, floating-point units are more complicated when accuracy becomes more of a concern. These qualities pertain to field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAs) used in the construction of circuits for floating point and multimode arithmetic. Floating point arithmetic units were invented by FPGA designers in the 90s. Area is the most important factor in any project. Although floating-point representations are better suitable for scientific computations than fixed-point representations, mathematical floating-point designs have become more complex. This is one reason why logarithmic number systems are better than floating point ones [2]. As a result, these programmes need a replacement for receiving binary numbers as input. Since the input to this adder/subtraction may lean into IEEE 754 format, this method saves time and makes the operation simpler to use [3]. The floating-point format uses 32 bits for single precision and 64 bits for double precision. A number of efforts have been made in the last several decades to improve the speed of floating point calculations [4].

1	8	23
Sign	Exponent	Mantissa

Fig 1. Single Precision

1	11	52
Sign	Exponent	Mantissa

Fig 2. Double Precision

The complexity of floating-point units rises when accuracy becomes the most essential concern, and they need more room and power than fixed-point multipliers. Floating-point units are also more complicated. The consequences of even a little error in accuracy may be enormous. Computational geometry and other scientific applications rely on accurate calculation criteria for climate modelling, a field that places a premium on floating-point accuracy. Nevertheless, excellent precision is not required for all applications. For these uses, an approximate and consistent value for the correct operation would do [5]. For less precise applications, it would be an honour to utilise double-precision floating point units. On the other hand, it makes latency worse. Xilinx is used for simulation, and the code is written in Verilog Hardware Description Language [6]. Then, Xilinx's ISE (integrated design suite) synthesises them. Part II covers floating-point additions and subtractions, Part III covers floating-point multipliers, Part IV covers floating-point numbers, Part V discusses the benefits and applications of floating-point numbers, and Section VI concludes the discussion.

FLOATING POINT NUMBERS ADDER/SUBTRACTOR

A fixed-point adder and auxiliary circuitry to handle signs, exponents, alignment before and after shift, standardisation after shift, and special

values are necessary for a floating-point adder/subtractor. Large and complicated data processing equipment, including DSP processors, graphics processors, and specific scientific programmes that use them, rely on floating point adders [7]. Thus, the adder ought to be very fast and have minimal latency. Due to the inherent complexity of adding floating points compared to integers, it must also be rather simple. Floating point algorithms were the subject of much study, and several prototypes were developed and tested. Therefore, greater simplification of the existing structures is the primary goal of this effort, with the secondary goal of lowering latency without sacrificing simplicity. Obtaining a new internal format for the operands (such as single or double extension) and reinstalling the secret conversion process while separating the sign, exponent, and significant aspects of each operand [8]. After that, there are exceptions and checks for specific operands. Using the difference between the two exponents, the orientation right shift and operand may be evaluated. Since the computed amount or difference needs to move left in the after-standardization stage, it is common practice to only provide pre-shifting functionality for one operand and substitute it with the other operand when one of them needs to be moved. This allows for the retention of several bits from the right-shifted operand, which are typically discharged when moving off the right end of the operand for the added purpose.

Fig 3. Block diagram of Adder/Subtractor

The important adder is thus usually larger than the two output numbers. Please note that the block diagram does not involve conversion between internal and external formats in the packaging process, as is the case with the unpacking stage. This is because the conversion of a broader sense to a narrower one requires rounding in order to achieve best results in the rounding process with the required production precision [9].

FLOATING POINT NUMBERS MULTIPLIER

Many applications rely on the multiplication of floating points, including image processing, signal processing, and many more. However, the functionality required by the application is different. others demand very little power, others very little latency, yet others very high accuracy, etc. The multiplication of floating-point numbers has found extensive usage in DSP space applications. The most critical component of

floating point multiplication is the mantissa multiplication that employs a 24x24 bit integer multiplier [10]. Using unique flow-point formats may be an optimal hardware solution for reconfigurable runtime. A floating point multiplier may function in one of six modes, each tailored to a certain application's accuracy or efficiency needs.

To further improve the multiplier's efficiency, optimal architecture with customised intellectual characteristics may be used to trim the inputs before multiplication. Enhanced machine speed is a result of faster multiplication. Floating point multipliers can handle overflow, underflow, and rounding in simple terms.

Fig 4. Block diagram of Multiplier

FLOATING POINT NUMBER DIVISION

A floating-point divider has the same overall structure as a floating-point multiplier. Fig 5 is generic block diagram for a floating-point divider.

packed into the required output format. Figure 5 demonstrates the slowest and most complex component of the unit. The two important ratios in $[1, 2)$ are within the range $(1/2, 2)$. Therefore, the result may have to be standardized by

Fig 5. Block diagram of Division

Unpacking and packing have the same functions as for floating point adders. The quotient sign is obtained with the operand signs XORing. The important divider is that two operators of the floating-point division are unpacked; the resulting components undergo several computational steps and the final result is

moving the preliminary exponent one position to the left and decreasing. Around the result can require more normalization and adjustment of exponent.

SIMULATION AND SYNTHESIS

5.1 Simulation After the implementation of RTL code of floating –point arithmetic adder/subtractor simulated the RTL code in Modelsim 6.4a. The simulator generated a waveform of floating-point adder/ subtractor is shown as.

for the purpose. There is another tool used for synthesis purpose is Xilinx. The device selected to synthesize the design, is called the “Target Device.” One can select any other suitable target device of Xilinx or other FPGA vendors like Actel, Altera, Cypress, Lattice, Lucent, Quick logic, etc. The program generates a summary of the synthesis activity and displays it as a “Sum File.” It gives a report on the utilization of the “Target Device” by the design that was synthesized. It also generates and display some timing information like “Critical Path Timing”.

Figure 6: Waveform generated through Simulator.

5.2 Synthesis Conversion of the code into hardware logic and fitting it into a FPGA or ASIC to realize the circuit is termed “Synthesis.” Used the Mentor Graphics Synthesis tool called “Leonardo Spectrum”

APPLICATION AND ADVANTAGES

Floating point numbers are widely used in digital applications including image

transformation, digital filters, and signal processing. The main difference between a DSP fixed and floating point is how the numerical data is represented. With a mantissa of 24 bits and an exponent of 8 bits, floating-point DSP that supports the industry-standard single-precision

operations. The exponential word width gives it a 16M precision range, which is far more dynamic than the fixed-point format. Even more precise are double-precision devices that are used in the industry; they have 64 bits, a 53-bit mantissa, and an 11-bit exponent.

CONCLUSION

This article provides a brief overview of floating-point numbers and their related operations, including adding, subtracting, multiplying, and dividing. This paper's findings indicate that the floating-point adder/subtractor algorithm written in Verilog was effectively implemented. After the simulation is finished, the floating-point adder code synthesised in Xilinx is also shown. There are several different software tools that are available for use in VLSI design. We have simulated the designs using Modelsim -Altera 6.4a. In this regard, it would like to bring to the attention of the researchers...

- The tools were shown just in their most basic form.
- Refer to the user manuals and Help menus for further information about the tools and the diversity of services they provide.

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